

Automated brain QSM computation pipeline deployed in the European Open Science Cloud.

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Motivation

Increased aging of the population in developed countries.

- Higher morbidity of neurodegenerative diseases.

Iron (Fe) accumulates in the brain throughout life.

- Abnormal Fe accumulation associated to neurodegeneration.
- Fe load can be used as an indicator of neurodegeneration.
 - Diagnostic/severity of diseases.
 - Normal aging → “Normality” look-up table.

French age pyramid

Fe load measure in vivo and non-invasive

Fe oxides possess **high susceptibility** → Generates magnetic field perturbations.

→ **MRI T2*** reflects Fe content

Magnitude: Relaxation rate (**R2***)

Phase: Quantitative susceptibility mapping (**QSM**)

Ultra-high magnetic fields.

→ High sensibility and resolution

→ More vulnerable to air/tissue interface effects.

Improper coil combination.

→ Artifacts in the phase reconstruction.

Existing software for QSM :

→ Mostly for 3T data (low susceptibility sensibility).

→ No means to overcome the possible data artifacts.

Goal

Examen :	Visit :	Inclusion	Annual visit
Consent			
History			
Genotyping			
Blood Biology (Biomarkers)			
Transcriptomic			
Neurologic Examination			
Neuropsychological Tests			
MRI 3T (90 min)			
MRI 7T (90 min)			
PET [¹¹ C]PIB			

QSM4SENIOR project:

- Re-evaluate Fe load measure parameters in aging.
- Obtain a quality look-up table of “normal aging”.
- Evaluate the sensitivity of QSM vs R2*.
- SENIOR database (78 **Healthy** subjects 54 - 79 y/o).

Pipeline for QSM from 3D multi-echo gradient echo.

- **Cloud based computation** (EOSC-Life Cloud).
- Phase pre-processing.
- Filtered field as MEDI input.

Multi-gradient-echo T2*-w acquisition (0.8 mm isotropic)

The pipeline

ISO27001-
certified
Openstack

14 cores
32 Go RAM
200 Go volume

$$\Delta W_{\Delta}^2 \Delta B_{in} = \Delta W_{\Delta}^2 \Delta B \text{ is calculated}$$

- Reduce the presence of artifacts:
→ Distortions due to strong B_0 .
→ Improper coil combination.

**SENIOR
deposit**

de Rochefort, L., et al. (2009). Proc Intl Soc Magnet Reson Med, 17(c), 1134.

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Reconstruction results

A: Laplacian of the phase with the filtered mask.
B: Filtered field map (RDF).
C: QSM obtained with the internal field.

* ROI segmentations obtained with VolBrain.

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Manjón JV. and Coupe P (2016).
Frontiers in Neuroinformatics.

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Results for QSM and R2* maps

Trend consistency between QSM and R2*.

Correlation with age e.g. Putamen

Linear regression slope steeper for QSM (1.43 ± 0.33) than R2* (0.7 ± 0.19).

Correlation between QSM and R2* ($r = 0.88, p < 0.01$)

*, $0.01 < p \leq 0.05$, **, $0.001 < p \leq 0.01$, ***, $1e-04 < p \leq 0.001$

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Discussion and conclusion

- QSM and R2* maps computation.
 - Automatic pipeline → Reduced artifacts.
 - Cloud-based reconstruction → Remote processing of research data.
 - Schedule the analyze of a whole cohort:
 - Import DICOM
 - Export results.
- Pipeline applied to the SENIOR database.
 - Results in line with the literature (same trend of the values).
 - Higher sensitivity and specificity allow to spot more subtle differences in the Fe load.
 - QSM higher sensitivity over R2*.
 - Look-up table of “normal” brain aging.
 - Iron load as biomarker.
- What next? → Comparison with patients (Alzheimer’s) database.

Thank you

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